

ATTITUDE TOWARDS QUIPPER AND BASIC COMPUTER SKILLS: PREDICTORS OF SCIENCE PERFORMANCE

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Attitude Towards Quipper and Basic Computer Skills: Predictors of Science Performance

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Abstract

During the COVID 19 pandemic, most schools implemented flexible learning with the help of the quipper platform due to the suspension of face-to-face classes. The primary purpose of this study was to seek a variable that best predicts pupils' academic performance in science. The sample size of 102 participants was selected using proportionate stratified random sampling. The descriptive correlational and causal design was employed in this study. Based on the data gathered, Grades 4, 5, and 6 levels have a highly positive overall mean level of pupils' Attitude towards Quipper regarding references and assignments and uses, respectively. Respondents have a proficient level of computer skills in terms of General Windows, and advanced level on Microsoft Word, Internet and Email, and Excel and Spreadsheet. The level of the Students' Academic Performance in Science was described as very satisfactory. The Attitude towards Quipper in terms of references and assignments and Computer skills in MS Word has a positive significant relationship to pupils' academic performance in science. As to the Attitude in uses, Computer skills in MS Word and Computer skills in MS Excel/ Spreadsheet, indicated that these variables are significant predictors with Attitude in uses being the best predictor.

Keywords: *attitude, online learning, quipper, academic performance, multiple regression*

Introduction

Breakthrough technology had integrated online platforms seamlessly as we transitioned toward flexible learning. Distance learning had been prominent amidst this pandemic, and the utilization of technology has been at the front line of the world's education for quite some time. The United States is the undisputed pioneer in online instruction in the nation today, with various online schools and a large number of online courses accessible to undergraduates. A recent report by the Sloan Consortium found that 6 million undergraduates in the US are taking online courses, almost 33% of each one of those taking on higher education. On the other hand, India also has a growing number of students taking online classes throughout Asia (ICEF Monitor, 2012). The Philippines also adopted this learning mode due to the increasing number of Covid19 cases in the country. Students worldwide were utilizing the online learning platform Quipper, which other countries are using: Japan, Indonesia, and Mexico (Dyquiango, 2017). As of the end of 2015, more than 1 million Filipino undergraduates have enrolled in the online platform, with nearly 70% coming from the National Capital Region (NCR). Almost 75 percent were in secondary school (Campos, 2016).

Science teachers have faced many challenges, especially at the elementary level. One such challenge in teaching science is the lack of student engagement, interest in school, teachers' dedication to their work, and teachers' integration of technology into their pedagogical approaches. Based on the belief in student engagement, learning improves when students are curious, attentive, or encouraged. Education tends to suffer when students are bored, dispassionate, disaffected, or uninterested. The teachers should be able to engage and motivate students to let them learn the basic competencies required. Teachers should be able to bring science lessons to life with real-world applications, understand student sensitivities and differences, and adjust science lesson plans based on students' assessment evaluations.

Science teachers are expected to use educational technology to deliver effective pedagogical instruction in science classrooms (National Science Teachers Association, 2015). Despite this expectation, many teachers are still uncertain about integrating technology into their classroom teaching. The challenges confronting teachers seeking to integrate technology into science classrooms are associated with various factors (Carver, 2016). One of the crucial factors reported was how teachers integrated technology into science classroom instruction to improve student learning outcomes (Carver, 2016). Adequate research was lacking regarding how teachers can effectively use educational technology tools for classroom instruction to enhance student-centered learning, engagement, performance, task accomplishment, and achievement in science (DePountis et al., 2015).

Compared to the other subjects taught in elementary, Science is the most logical subject for understanding most of the concepts that govern the environment. Philippine environmental education has not been in its best situation. Philippine education's anchor on Science has been very weak. (Magnanimous Science; 2014).

According to Cimer (2012), the three reasons made learning biology difficult. (Cimer, 2012) Many concepts and biological events that cannot be seen with the naked eye are too abstract/not visible; and (Konicek-Moran, 2015) some students mentioned that the time available to study biology was insufficient. As a result, students' understanding of their learned material became low.

Liceo de Cagayan University has been one of the partner schools to adapt and integrate this online learning. Senior High School started last 2018-2019, while the Junior High School started in the school year 2019-2020. It has been adopted by the elementary students for two years already. Thus, the platform had been a great help in these trying times, and this had been one of the Computer-Assisted

Instructions of the institution in conveying learning materials, such as audio recordings, videos, graphics, and text that enhance the students' learning process.

Computer-assisted instruction (CAI) is an instructional approach wherein a computer is utilized for instructional materials and assessing the learning outcomes.

Drill and practice include a sequence of tasks, exercises, or words repeatedly until they can be performed impeccably (Zubairu & Musa 2020).

Tutorials present ideas, concepts, skills, and abilities to students and allow them to practice often. It additionally benefits individualized instruction, addresses feedback based on the students' progress and can be used as a remediation for students who missed the activity.

A simulation depicts an actual event or circumstances where students can see the results of their assigned task. Students see the results of their selection immediately. It is an approximate imitation of the operation of a process or system that represents its operation over time. The simulation addresses higher-order thinking skills. With these, the researcher assessed the online learning performance of Grades 4 to 6 pupils in Science using Computer-Assisted Instruction such as Quipper. The researcher believes this research will help improve the pupils' interest in learning different tasks and develop a positive attitude towards learning online.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the pupils' academic performance in science using the Quipper online Platform. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of pupils' attitude towards Quipper in terms of:
 - 1.1. references and assignments; and
 - 1.2. uses for online classes?
2. What is the level of the basic computer skills of the pupils in terms of:
 - 2.1. general windows;
 - 2.2. Microsoft words;
 - 2.3. internet and email; and
 - 2.4. Microsoft excel/spreadsheet?
3. What is the level of pupils' academic performance in elementary science?
4. Is there a significant relationship between pupils' academic performance in science, attitude towards Quipper, and computer skills?
5. Which of the variables best predicts pupils' academic performance in science?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used the descriptive-correlational and causal research design. This design was used to describe the relationship between the online learning performance of the grade school pupils and the computer-assisted instruction variables. According to (Mertler, 2014), the purpose of descriptive studies is to describe and interpret the current status of individuals, settings, conditions, or events. In descriptive research, the researcher was studying the phenomenon of interest as it exists. Naturally, no attempt is made to manipulate the individuals, conditions, or events. Correlational research is discovering and then possibly measuring relationships between two or more variables. In education, the correlational study seeks out traits, abilities, or conditions that covary or co-relate. Meanwhile, McCombes (2020) stated that a correlational research design measures a relationship between two variables without the researcher controlling either. It aims to determine whether there is either a positive or negative correlation.

Respondents

The study participants were the grades 4 to 6 pupils of Liceo de Cagayan University, Grade School Department, enrolled in this school year 2021-2022 with a total population of 111 students. Of the 111, 39 students were in Grade 4, 35 students were Grade 5, and 37 students were Grade 6. Of this number, 102 pupils were used as the participants of this study and who were selected using proportionate stratified random sampling.

Table 1. *Sample Sizes by Level and Student Population*

Level	Population Size	Sample Size
Grade 4	39	34
Grade 5	35	34
Grade 6	37	34
Total Students	111	102

The total sample size is 102, based on Slovin's formula. This was proportionally allocated to each level - the sub-sample sizes, to fully represent all the student groups in Grade 4-6 Levels Grade School.

Instrument

The researcher used two adapted questionnaires in this study, namely, the survey questionnaire on pupils' attitude towards the use of online/quipper platform adapted from the study of Cakrawati (2017) and the self-assessment basic computer skills questionnaire adapted from the study of Isaac (2015.). Moreover, the pupils' grades in Science for the school year 2020-2021 were used as the indicator of their academic performance in Science. Moreover, in determining the students' academic achievement, the general average (GWA) in the First and Second Grading of each student in the sample will be used. Items were prepared using a 5-point Likert type scale, including "strongly agree," "agree," "neutral," "disagree," and "strongly disagree," for the Students' Attitude Towards Quipper Survey Questionnaire and the Self-Assessment Basic Computer Skills Survey Questionnaire.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

Before scaling for complete research, a pilot study was initiated with thirty students from different levels. The collected questionnaire was analyzed to determine whether the data collected helped the researcher meet the study's objectives. To test the reliability of the scale, the item-total test score correlation and the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient value of items were calculated and examined. The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient value measures the internal consistency between the test scores of a scale. The values above 0.70 were accepted as adequate for the test reliability. The item-total test score correlation is used to explain the relationship between the score of each item and the total score of all test items. The item-total test score correlation was high and positive, indicating that the scale has internal consistency. Hence, Cronbach's coefficient of 0.94 was adequate for full-scale data collection.

Procedure

After all the necessary permissions had been received, the researcher floated instruments to the participants of this study and the intervention conditions. The researcher conducted the survey to all grades 4, 5 and 6 pupils of Liceo de Cagayan University for the school year 2021-2022. However, the students may withdraw from the research anytime, not forcing anyone to answer the questionnaire. All the personal information of the participants were dealt with utmost confidentiality. For Science Academic Performance, the average grades for the first and second grading were used.

Data Analysis

Mean and standard deviation were used to determine the level of pupils' attitude towards Quipper; level of computer skills of the pupils, and the academic performance in Science. On one hand, Pearson R correlation was used to determine the relationship between the variables. Lastly, multiple regression was employed to determine the variable that best predicts pupils' academic performance in Science.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure the quality and reliability of research findings, the researcher observed the following University Research Protocol:

First, the researcher sought approval from the adviser after carefully reviewing the manuscript for the final defense. Then, the researcher completed the Research Ethics Application Form and submitted it to the Office of the Research Ethics Board with the approved research proposal. The Director of the Research Ethics Board Office reviewed the proposal and Research Ethics Form for completeness and compliance with the University format and guidelines. The researcher wrote letters and secured permission from the Dean of School of Teacher Education, and School Principal to conduct the study to all Grades 4, 5 and 6 students of Liceo de Cagayan University. The researcher also secured the parents' consent to allow their child to participate in the study. Moreover, the researcher assured that the survey would not harm in any manner and, whatever the result, would be held with the utmost confidentiality. In the provision of the final manuscript, the researcher provided the adviser with a copy of the manuscript for assessment and review of the quality and relevance of the paper before scheduling the final research presentation. After which the Dean of the School of Teacher Education approved the schedule for the final defense of the thesis after a thorough assessment and review of the final manuscript.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data collected from the participants.

Problem 1. What is the level of pupils' attitude towards Quipper in terms of references and assignments, and uses for online classes?

Table 2 presents the Mean Distribution of the Level of Pupils' Attitude towards Quipper in terms of References and Assignments. As shown in the table, the pupils showed the highest attitude for item number 9 "Quipper is convenient to use especially in submitting assignments," with a mean of 4.37 followed by item number 7 "The assignments posted by my teacher in Quipper help me to improve my learning" with a mean of 4.36. On the other hand, pupils obtained the lowest attitude for item number 10 "The online activities and discussions in Quipper can motivate me to learn more about the lesson" with a mean of 4.17 followed by item number 6 "The reference

articles posted by my teacher in Quipper help me to understand the contents/ topics of the lesson better” with a mean of 4.18. The overall mean is 4.28, implying that the pupils were highly optimistic about Quipper using the online platform for references and assignments.

Table 2. Mean Distribution of the Level of Pupils' Attitude towards Quipper in terms of References and Assignments

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interj
1 The reference videos posted by my teacher in Quipper help me to improve my learning.	4.19	.975	Agree	Highly Positive
2 The reference videos posted by my teacher in Quipper help me to understand the contents/ topics of the lesson better.	4.27	.869	Agree	Highly Positive
3 The reference PowerPoint files posted by my teacher in Quipper help me to improve my learning.	4.31	.808	Agree	Highly Positive
4 The reference PowerPoint files posted by my teacher in Quipper help me to understand the contents/ topics of the lesson better.	4.23	.880	Agree	Highly Positive
5 The reference articles posted by my teacher in Quipper help me to improve my learning.	4.34	.802	Agree	Highly Positive
6 The reference articles posted by my teacher in Quipper help me to understand the contents/ topics of the lesson better.	4.18	.898	Agree	Highly Positive
7 The assignments posted by my teacher in Quipper help me to improve my learning.	4.36	.841	Agree	Highly Positive
8 The assignments posted by my teacher in Quipper help me to understand the contents/ topics of the lesson better.	4.34	.895	Agree	Highly Positive
9. Quipper is convenient to use especially in submitting assignments.	4.37	.952	Agree	Highly Positive
10 The online activities and discussions in Quipper can motivate me to learn more about the lesson.	4.17	.979	Agree	Highly Positive
Overall Mean	4.28	0.89	Agree	Highly Positive

Note: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very Highly Positive; 3.50-4.49, Agree, Highly Positive; 2.50-3.49, Neutral, Moderately Positive; 1.50-2.49, Disagree, Highly Negative; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Highly Negative.

This finding supported the claim of Pitagan (2017) that students were motivated to explore activities and encouraged to submit works in Quipper. Most students utilized this online platform for their assignments and to deepen their grasp of the topic (Agustina, 2017). Furthermore, Pitagan (2017), concluded that students with constant or periodic exposure to Quipper were more likely to achieve high test scores and keep the attendance rate high.

Thus, this implies Quipper has a good impact on students' learning and development, knowing that it is convenient to use and students can open all the materials they need in studying the subject anytime and anywhere as long as the teacher posts it in their Quipper assignment section. Moreover, they don't need to go to school to attend class. Having said that, there are no hindrances for them to be on time in submitting their homework as long as they have a stable internet connection.

Table 3 presents the Mean Distribution of the Level of Pupils' Attitude towards Quipper in terms of Uses. As depicted in the Table, the pupils obtained the highest mean for item number 14, "The use of Quipper makes my learning experiences more interesting," with a mean of 4.28, followed by item number 15, "The use of Quipper increases the effectiveness of learning" with a mean of 4.24.

On the other hand, pupils obtained their lowest mean for item number 18 "I prefer reading my courses in paper form instead of reading them through Quipper," with a mean of 3.40 followed by item number 20 "It is easy to use Quipper because of the slow-speed internet on my mobile gadgets" with a mean of 3.50. The overall mean is 3.94, which revealed that the pupils were highly positive in using the Quipper software.

Table 3. Mean Distribution of the Level of Pupils' Attitude towards Quipper in terms of Uses

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
11 The use of Quipper saves effort and time.	4.17	1.04	Agree	Highly Positive
12 The use of Quipper helps me practice my language skills.	4.01	.954	Agree	Highly Positive
Continued...				
13. The use of Quipper helps me acquiring new vocabulary.	4.12	.940	Agree	Highly Positive
14. The use of Quipper makes my learning experiences more interesting.	4.28	.937	Agree	Highly Positive
15. The use of Quipper increases the effectiveness of learning.	4.24	.969	Agree	Highly Positive
16. The use of Quipper facilitates interaction and communication between teacher and students.	4.01	1.09	Agree	Highly Positive
17. It is easy to use Quipper as a mobile learning application.	3.73	1.53	Agree	Highly Positive
18. I prefer reading my courses in paper form instead of reading them through Quipper.	3.40	1.36		Moderately Positive
19. It is easy to use Quipper as a mobile learning application.	3.95	1.52	Agree	Highly Positive
20. It is easy to use Quipper because of the slow-speed internet on my mobile gadgets.	3.50	1.362	Agree	Highly Positive
Overall Mean	3.94	1.17	Agree	Highly Positive

Note: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very Highly Positive; 3.50-4.49, Agree, Highly Positive; 2.50-3.49, Neutral, Moderately Positive; 1.50-2.49, Disagree, Highly Negative; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Highly Negative.

This finding supported the claim of Diva et al. (2022) that students are interested in the Quipper application, especially that it gives some benefits for their learning, including flexibility in terms of time and location for learning, as well as the ability to adapt many sorts of learning styles to keep them engaged in studying. The findings align with what El Iq Bali et al. (2021) stated: students' interest in learning is more significant when using the Quipper School than conventional learning. Much more so, because Quipper has unique features and tools that make it more engaging to use, especially for the student's welfare. It is easy, flexible, and convenient to use, making it more effective in terms of their learning.

Problem 2. What is the level of computer skills of the pupils in terms of general windows, Microsoft words, internet and email, and Microsoft excel/spreadsheet?

Table 4 presents the Mean Distribution for the Level of Computer Skills in terms of General Windows. As reflected in the Table, the pupils have the highest general window skill for item number 2, "I can identify the 'backspace' key on the keyboard," with a mean of 4.66, while the lowest mean is for item number 3 with a mean of 4.55. The overall mean is 4.51, implying that the pupils have proficient computer skills in general windows. This finding supported the research study by Komba and David (2016), which results were 95.0% of elementary students could turn on a computer by pressing the power button. On the other side, 5.0% were unable to turn on the computer.

These data suggest that most students could turn on a computer by pressing the power-on button. Based on these statistics, it appears that the majority of the students in this survey had no trouble starting a computer.

Furthermore, 75% of the students could locate the Start Menu, whereas 25.0% could not. These data suggest that most students were aware of another critical technique for shutting down a computer: locating the Start Menu on the desktop. Thus, these previous findings have the same outcome as this present research study that the Level of Computer Skills in terms of General Windows among the Elementary Pupils was proficient, which means that they are skillful in this category. In a nutshell, it indicates that the teacher-pupil interactions during their computer class in their previous years were effective, especially in utilizing the essential buttons and general windows.

Table 4. Mean Distribution for the Level of Computer Skills in terms of General Windows

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I can identify the 'End' key on the keyboard.	4.32	1.12	Agree	Advanced
Continued...				
2. I can identify the 'backspace' key on the keyboard.	4.66	.824	Strongly Agree	Proficient
3. I can drag and drop objects using a mouse.	4.55	.827	Strongly Agree	Proficient
4. I can log on to a computer using a password.	4.50	.951	Strongly Agree	Proficient
Overall Mean	4.51	0.93	Strongly Agree	Proficient

Note: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree, Proficient; 3.50-4.49, Agree, Advanced; 2.50-3.49, Neutral, Intermediate; 1.50-2.49, Disagree, Basic; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree, Fundamental.

Table 5 presents the Mean Distribution for the Level of Computer Skills in terms of Microsoft Word. As depicted in the Table, the pupils obtained the highest mean for item number 7, "I can name a document before saving it," with a mean of 4.54, and the lowest mean for item number 9, "I can close the Microsoft word application using the long method" with a mean of 3.84. The overall mean is 4.21, which revealed that the pupils have advanced skills in Microsoft word application. This finding supported the claim of Grant, Malloy, and Murphy (2009) with their one-tailed z statistic test that revealed more than half of students had a high degree of proficiency in Word Processing programs, for instance, MS Word. This is for the reason that students have grown more familiar with computers than students a generation before as a result of numerous other technological improvements such as internet use, chat rooms, text messaging, and the pervasive use of computers in homes and classrooms during the last decades which fosters their confidence in computer use.

Table 5. Mean Distribution for the Level of Computer Skills in terms of Microsoft Word

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
5. I can open Microsoft word using the start menu	4.22	1.09	Agree	Advanced
6. I can save a document in a specified location	4.39	.924	Agree	Advanced
7. I can name a document before saving it	4.54	.791	Strongly Agree	Proficient
8. I can print a document	4.05	1.32	Agree	Advanced
9. I can close the Microsoft word application using the long method	3.84	1.25	Agree	Advanced
Overall Mean	4.21	1.07	Agree	Advanced

Note: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree, Proficient; 3.50-4.49, Agree, Advanced; 2.50-3.49, Neutral, Intermediate; 1.50-2.49, Disagree, Basic; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree, Fundamental.

In line with this, the research by Komba and David (2016) showed that 85.0% could start a new document, whereas the remaining 15.0% couldn't. These data indicate that the vast majority of the students in this study were able to open a new document in a Microsoft Office word application. These data suggest that the vast majority of the students in this study were able to open a new document in a Microsoft Office word application. Moreover, students who were able to save a typed document accounted for 68.4% of all students, whereas those who could not do so accounted for 31.7%. As a result of the outcomes of this study, it can be stated that most students possessed the fundamental skills required to utilize a new document using Microsoft Office Word.

Table 6 presents the Mean Distribution for the Level of Computer Skills in terms of Internet and Email. As shown in the Table, the pupils obtained the highest mean for item number 17, "I can send a reply to an email," with a mean of 4.52, followed by item number 12, "I can use Google and search the web for keywords" with a mean of 4.42. On the other hand, the lowest mean is for item number 18, "I can copy a recipient on an email," with a mean of 4.02, followed by item number 13, "I can read a topic that is hyperlinked," with a mean of 4.03. The overall mean is 4.27, which implies that the pupils have advanced computer skills in using the internet and emails.

Table 6. Mean Distribution for the Level of Computer Skills in terms of Internet and Email

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
10. I can launch or open the Internet explorer	4.14	1.21	Agree	Advanced
Continued...				
11. I can type a website address and access it	4.27	1.05	Agree	Advanced
12. I can use Google and search the web for keywords	4.42	.894	Agree	Advanced
13. I can read a topic that is hyperlinked	4.03	1.16	Agree	Advanced
14. I can update the display of a current web page	4.33	.936	Agree	Advanced
15. I can go to the web page that was previously displayed	4.36	.962	Agree	Advanced
16. I can open an unread e-mail on outlook	4.26	1.07	Agree	Advanced
17. I can send a reply to an e-mail	4.52	.792	Strongly Agree	Proficient
18. I can copy a recipient on an e-mail	4.02	1.18	Agree	Advanced
19. I can attach a document to an e-mail	4.37	.984	Agree	Advanced
Overall Mean	4.27	1.02	Agree	Advanced

Note: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree, Proficient; 3.50-4.49, Agree, Advanced; 2.50-3.49, Neutral, Intermediate; 1.50-2.49, Disagree, Basic; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree, Fundamental.

This finding contrasted with the study by Komba and David (2016) that looked at how well students could utilize the internet to find information among Tanzanian primary school students. The researchers examined three indicators to determine whether or not students possessed the fundamental abilities needed to search for web content; the two indicators had a strong association for this study. It was found that 56.7% were able to launch a web browser such as Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Internet Explorer, or Opera, while 43.3% were unable. It suggests that more than half of the students could open a web browser, with a considerable minority unable to. This is contrary to the new result since most students have advanced computer skills in opening an Internet Explorer compared to the previous study.

Additionally, in the second indicator, 56.0% were able to input the correct key phrases to find information from the internet, whereas 44.0% were unable. As a result, while more than half of the students could enter the correct key terms while looking for information on websites, a substantial number of students were unable. Still, it contrasted with the previous study as the new research shows that the primary students from Liceo de Cagayan University have higher computer skills in searching the web for keywords since they were taught about these skills in their computer subject.

Table 7. Mean Distribution for the Level of Computer Skills in terms of Excel and Spreadsheet

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
20. I can enter data in a cell on an Excel spreadsheet	3.95	1.13	Agree	Advanced
21. I can change the font size of a text in a selected cell	4.27	1.02	Agree	Advanced
22. I can fill color in a cell on the Excel spreadsheet	4.10	1.11	Agree	Advanced
23. I can add (sum) the data in two cells	3.99	1.11	Agree	Advanced
24. I can write text in a cell	4.30	1.02	Agree	Advanced
25. I can perform other functions of excel	3.97	1.13	Agree	Advanced
Overall Mean	4.10	1.09	Agree	Advanced

Note: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree, Proficient; 3.50-4.49, Agree, Advanced; 2.50-3.49, Neutral, Intermediate; 1.50-2.49, Disagree, Basic; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree, Fundamental.

Table 7 presents the Mean Distribution for the Level of Computer Skills in terms of Excel and Spreadsheet. As depicted in the Table, the pupils have obtained the highest mean for item number 24, "I can write text in a cell," with a mean of 4.30, while the lowest mean is for item number 20, "I can enter data in a cell on an Excel spreadsheet" with a mean of 3.95. The overall mean is 4.10, which revealed that the pupils have advanced computer skills for internet and email applications. This finding supported the claim of Grant, Malloy, and Murphy (2009) that an average of 69% of their participants from North Carolina who utilize spreadsheets to obtain, analyze, interpret, synthesize, apply and present data were classified as having average or high spreadsheet skills proficiency, according to the findings of the one-tailed z statistic test. Thus, it depicts that this new research study has a greater level of computer skills in Excel and Spreadsheet compared to other countries, particularly in North Carolina, and having their stock knowledge in utilizing Spreadsheets and Excel at school made it possible for them to be computer literate.

Problem 3. What is the level of pupils' academic performance in science?

Table 8. Overall Mean for the Level of Pupils' Academic Performance in Science

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Grades	102	77.50	98.00	88.55	5.54	Very Satisfactory

Table 8 presents the Overall Mean for the Level of Pupils' Academic Performance in Science. As shown in the Table, of the 102 participants, the lowest grade obtained was 77.5, while the highest grade obtained was 98. The overall mean is 88.55, which implies that the academic performance of the students in Science under the use of Quipper is very satisfactory. This finding supported the claim of Espineli & Rodil (2018), which reveals that the experimental group's performance in Science was better than the control group's after being exposed to Quipper for a month, and it was attained because of the feasibility of employing Quipper School as a teaching tool in the classroom in which the materials and instructions are easily accessible among the students.

However, it contrasted to the findings of Barakter (2000) and Mahmood (2004) that there may have a small positive effect on student's performance if they utilize CAI in their learning compared with their performance in their in-person classes because the result of this research is beyond satisfactory which means that it is not just small positive effect to student's performance if they utilize Quipper as a mode of learning instead of a traditional class, particularly in Science subject

Problem 4. Is there a significant relationship between pupils' academic performance in science, attitude towards Quipper, and computer skills?

Table 9. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Analysis for the significant relationship between Pupils' Academic Performance in Science, Attitude towards Quipper, and Computer Skills

Variable	N	R	P-Value	Interpretation
Attitude in Terms of References and Assignments	102	.243	.014	Significant
Attitude in Terms of Uses	102	.004	.966	Not Significant
Computer Skill in General Windows	102	.136	.172	Not Significant
Computer Skill in MS Word	102	.283	.004	Significant
Computer Skill in Internet and Email	102	.132	.187	Not Significant
Computer Skill in MS Excel and Spreadsheet	102	.032	.750	Not Significant

Table 9 shows the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Analysis for the significant relationship between Pupils' Academic Performance in Science, Attitude towards Quipper, and Computer Skills. As depicted in the Table, the attitude in terms of uses (P-.966), computer skills in terms of general windows (P-.172), Internet and Emails (P-.187), and MS Excel and Spreadsheet (P-.750) have probability (P) values higher than the alpha value of 0.05 which indicate that there was no significant relationship between the pupils' academic performance in Science and the said variables. On the other hand, the attitude in terms of references and assignments (P-.014) and computer skills in MS Word (P-.004) has probability (P) values lower than the alpha value of 0.05, which indicate that there was a positive significant relationship between the pupils' academic performance and the said variables. This means that when

the attitude in using the references and assignments and computer skills in MS Word will increase, the pupils' academic performance will also increase. This finding supported the claim of Septinawati (2020) et al. that Quipper maintains interaction between teacher and student in and out of the classroom, allowing students to receive lessons or review material even when the teacher is not present in the classroom to provide direct instruction. Students can improve their learning achievement by reviewing material, and the new learning system enhances students' learning experiences.

Due to the accessibility and convenience of utilizing Quipper among the students, they can review the materials wherever and whenever they are in which they are not stressed out to comply with all the tasks within the class hours, same as the past face-to-face classes. Thus, they can open the Quipper if ready to comply with the tasks.

Problem 5. Which of the variables best predicts pupils' academic performance in science?

Table 10. Multiple Regression Analysis to Determine the Variable that Best Predicts Academic Performance in Science.

Variable/Predictor	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	P-Value	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	54.47	10.50		5.18	.000	
Attitude in References and Assignment	3.60	1.197	.414	3.01	.003	Significant
Attitude in Uses	4.39	1.607	.594	-2.73	.007	Significant
Computer Skill in General Window	-1.89	1.460	-.249	-1.29	.197	Not Significant
Computer Skill in MS Word	6.49	2.560	.240	2.53	.013	Significant
Computer Skill in Internet and Email	6.21	3.404	.677	1.82	.071	Not Significant
Computer Skill in MS Excel/ Spreadsheet	2.11	.996	.332	-2.12	.036	Significant
R=.464, R ² =.216, F=4.35(P-Value=.001)						

Table 10 presents the Summary of Multiple Regression Analyses for Variables Predicting Students' Academic Performance in Science. The R-value of 0.464 indicates a moderate positive correlation between the predictors and academic performance. The R² value of 0.216 indicates that the predictors explain 21.6% of the variability of the pupils' academic performance in Science. Meanwhile, the P-value of 0.001 implies a significant relationship between the predictor variables and academic performance. Furthermore, the regression output above shows that computer skill in the general window (P-.197) and computer skill in MS Excel/Spreadsheet (P-.071) have P-values higher than the alpha value of 0.05, which implies that these variables failed to predict the academic performance of pupils in Science. On the other hand, pupils' attitude in using the references and assignments (P-.003), attitude in uses of Quipper (P-.007), computer skill in MS Word (P-.013), and computer skill in MS Excel and spreadsheet (P-.036) have probability (P) values lower than the alpha value of 0.05 which implied that these said variables significantly predicted the pupils' academic performance in Science whereby the best predictor is the pupils' attitude in Quipper uses with the Standardized Coefficients beta value of .594.

Based on the Unstandardized Coefficients B value, the regression equation model is $Y=54.47 + 3.6X_1 + 4.39X_2 + 6.49X_3 + 2.11X_4$. This means that for every one point increase on attitude in references and assignments, the academic performance will have an increase of 3.6; one point increase in attitude in uses, 4.39 increase in academic performance; one point increase in computer skill in MS Word, the increase in academic performance is 6.49, and one point increase in computer skill in MS Excel and spreadsheet, the increase in academic performance is 2.11.

This finding supports the conclusion of Cakrawati (2017) that 67.5% of the students agreed that Quipper tools provided by their professors increase their learning and understanding of the classes, making them convenient to use, particularly when completing homework. Furthermore, the large gap between agreeing and neutral or disagree suggests that students respond well to Quipper regarding the materials' relevance, accessibility, and motivation to study more about the relevant subjects.

In addition, according to Saptani (2017), the assignment menu is the most beneficial aspect of Quipper since it gives a lot of activities

for students to practice more in their lectures discussed by their lecturers. Thus, the references and assignments posted on the Quipper website should be accessible and instructed very well by the teachers so that students can answer and review the lessons quickly.

Conclusions

This study aimed to predict the academic performance of the pupils utilizing the Quipper online platform in Science and their fundamental computer abilities. It also looked at which variables best predict pupils' scientific academic performance. Based on the findings, the study showed that the students' attitudes regarding Quipper were highly positive in terms of utilizing references, completing tasks, and using Quipper.

Pupils also showed proficient and advanced computer skills, essential in using the Quipper software as their lesson content.

Pupils showed interest in Quipper as a medium of learning tool that could motivate them to learn more and increase their academic performance in Science. From the students' perspective, the results showed that Quipper is an effective medium for learning since it stimulated their interest in studying the content.

The attitude towards Quipper in terms of references and assignments and Computer Skills in MS Word also has a positive significant relationship to pupils' academic performance in Science. This helps teachers in determining the pupil's academic performance in Science and serves as a guide to teachers for future undertakings.

Among the variables that best predict students' academic performance, the pupil's attitude in using Quipper has the highest Standardized Coefficients of beta value. Students respond well to Quipper in terms of the materials' relevance, accessibility, uses, and drive to learn more about the software content.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are recommended:

The school administrators may continue utilizing Quipper to assist teachers in teaching-learning management. Teachers may also receive training to better prepare them with the necessary technological, professional, and pedagogical abilities for using Quipper in an online classroom environment.

Teachers may use other Quipper programs that haven't been completely utilized, incorporate valuable information, a variety of activities, and evaluations that are appropriate for the subject being covered, and thereby create lesson content that adheres to the curriculum.

Students are encouraged to explore and become familiar with various features of Quipper to fully utilize the software applications and learn and answer assignments at their convenience.

Parents may assess their child's performance and guide them in their future endeavors.

For future researchers, the study can be replicated to include bigger sample size and other variables that affect pupils' academic performance in Science.

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